

Open research, data sharing and opportunities in ethics processes

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of Melbourne

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

This project aimed to discover how data sharing is impacted by ethics processes. It did this by testing the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) recommendations regarding future-proofing ethics applications (found in framework Open Research and Data Publication element) in two ways. First, a review of ethics training, support and policies was undertaken. Second was a deeper investigation to map the ethics application process at the University of Melbourne.

Review of Training, Support and Policies

This discovery phase involved a scan of relevant, up-to-date principles and frameworks related to data sharing and examining if and how these were reflected in training, support and policies at the institution. We looked in particular at the FAIR principles, the Sorbonne Declaration on research data rights, the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research (and the associated Management of Data and Information guide) and also the University's Principles for Open Access to Research Outputs.

Mapping the Ethics Process

To examine where data sharing was included in the ethics process (including the wider training and support provided to applicants) and whether this impeded data sharing practices we undertook three overlapping activities. The first was documenting the actual ethics application associated with this current project. Second, a workshop was held with engaged data-sharing researchers at the university and third, an examination of ethics documents supplied by workshop participants.

These activities identified areas within the ethics process that hindered the sharing of research data and identified where further action or investigation could be taken.

Resulting Improvements

Given the complexity and many stakeholders involved in the ethics processes, we did not expect to realise an immediate improvement in research data management (RDM) at the University. The project has, however, established a solid basis on which to move forward with improved practices.

Being able to investigate ethics processes through an RDM lens has provided actionable insights that will be able to be taken further through additional work. Further, in convening a reference group of senior stakeholders for the project, we have established the need for improvements and have the authority to initiate these further investigations.

Next Steps

Many areas for improvement and further investigations have been identified and are outlined in a discussion paper. These will be pursued over the coming months.

Project Outputs

Ethics and Data Discussion Paper, The University of Melbourne. <https://doi.org/10.26188/20500101>

The discussion paper details our findings, insights and recommendations. It highlights aspects of the ethics process that hinder data sharing and also identifies opportunities and recommendations for further action and investigation in order to improve data sharing within the ethics process. The paper could be used by other universities to examine their own research ethics processes through the lens of data sharing. Given the University of Melbourne has developed a robust and mature ethics process, the insights may be less useful. However, it provides an approach for investigating these issues and potential leads for areas of improvement in data sharing.

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